

Isotopic Exchange Reactions : Part III. Exchange of Chlorine between Acetyl chloride and Bismuth oxychloride

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Exchange studies in homogeneous solution reveal complete exchange of chlorine between acetyl chloride and labelled bismuth oxychloride. This is explained on the basis of the formation of BiOCl_2^- and BiOCl_3^- ions, the existence of which is supported by conductance and transport measurements.

In an earlier communication¹ from this laboratory it is reported that rapid and complete exchange of chlorine occurs between liquid acetyl chloride and soluble benzyldimethylphenylammonium chloride. Bromine exchange studies with soluble tetrasubstituted ammonium bromides in liquid acetyl bromide² also reveal complete exchange of bromine within the time of separation. Insoluble sodium chloride³ does not exchange chlorine with liquid acetyl chloride whereas cadmium chloride⁴, though insoluble in acetyl chloride, shows rapid but partial exchange of chlorine. This behaviour of cadmium chloride has been attributed to its capacity to form insoluble complex compound with acetyl chloride. Bismuth oxychloride dissolves in acetyl chloride to give orange coloured solution from which a red viscous liquid of composition $\text{BiCl}_3 \cdot (\text{CH}_3\text{CO})_2\text{O}$ has been isolated by Paul *et al.*⁴. It is possible to represent this compound by the alternative formation, $(\text{CH}_3\text{CO})_2^+(\text{BiOCl}_2)^-$. Further, the nature of the species present in the solution may be different from the isolated compound. It is, therefore, of interest to investigate the solvent interaction in the solution of bismuth oxychloride in acetyl chloride by chlorine exchange studies. Conductance and transport measurements have also been carried out to throw light on the nature of the species present in the solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals and reagents were of A. R. quality. Characteristics of tracer chlorine-36 and the method of purification of acetyl chloride are given in reference 1. Labelled bismuth oxychloride was prepared by dissolving bismuth oxide in hydrochloric acid containing chlorine-36 and diluting the solution with water. The precipitated bismuth oxychloride was centrifuged, washed with water, dried at 110-120° and analysed for Bi and Cl. (Required: Bi-80.31%; Cl-13.63%; Found Bi-80.36%, Cl-14.03%). It was further dried over P_2O_5 in vacuo just before exchange runs. Exchange runs were carried out in the same

1. Desai and Halder, *This Journal*, 1964, 41, 116.
2. Desai and Halder, *Proc. Nucl. and Rad. Chem. Symposium*, Waltair, January 20-22, 1966, 255.
3. Desai and Halder, *This Journal*, 1966, 43, 734.
4. Paul, Singh and Sandhu, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 319.

manner as reported earlier¹. Activities of samples of infinite thickness were measured with an end-window type G. M. counter.

Pure acetyl chloride was distilled into an evacuated conductivity cell containing BiOCl, which was then sealed. Conductance measurements of solutions of bismuth oxychloride in acetyl chloride were taken at $28 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with the conductivity bridge, type C 101-02, (Toehniwal Instruments, Bombay) working at 50C/S, or 30KC/S from an internal oscillator and provided with a sensitive magic eye detector.

Transport experiments were carried out in a closed all glass apparatus without stop-cocks described by Fairbrother and Scott². The apparatus was filled with solution *in vacuo* and then sealed. A current of 200-500 microamperes was passed through the solution for 4 to 6 hrs. at a potential difference of 50 volts between the two platinum electrodes. Evolution of gas or separation of solid on the electrodes was not observed. At the end of an experiment the anode and cathode compartments were separated by tilting the apparatus, whereby the connection between them was broken and the solution in each compartment was analysed for bismuth and chlorine.

TABLE I

Exchange of chlorine between acetyl chloride (AcCl) and labelled bismuth oxychloride.

Expt. No.	Weight of AcCl in grams.	Weight of BiOCl in grams.	Specific activity of BiOCl, c/m/g. of Cl.	Time of contact in min.	Substance	Activity counts/min.
I	4.466	0.2843	3.65×10^6	14	AcCl	669 ± 12
				30	-do-	667 ± 12
				62	-do-	684 ± 12
				122	-do-	669 ± 12
				—	Residue	670 ± 12
II	1.5710	0.1067	9.97×10^6	10	AcCl	2270 ± 48
				15	-do-	2290 ± 48
				30	-do-	2300 ± 48
				—	Residue	2210 ± 47
III*	2.200	0.5799	3.26×10^6	1	AcCl	1621 ± 18
				4	-do-	1614 ± 18
				9	-do-	1637 ± 18
				15	-do-	1656 ± 18
				30	-do-	1611 ± 18
				60	-do-	1642 ± 18
				—	Residue	1632 ± 18

*In the absence of light.

DISCUSSION

Exchange studies (Table I) reveal complete exchange of chlorine between bismuth oxychloride and acetyl chloride within the time required for the separation of components.

Although it is tempting to cite the fast exchange of chlorine as an evidence in support of self-ionization of acetyl chloride and /or ionization of bismuth oxychloride, other possibilities are not excluded. A direct reaction of bismuth oxychloride with acetyl chloride as shown below can explain the observed rapid exchange of chlorine.

BiOCl_2^- and BiOCl_3^{--} ions may be expected to be labile with respect to chloride ion exchange. The results of chemical analysis of the residue left after exchange runs suggest that it contains bismuth and chlorine in the ratio of 1:3, in agreement with the observations made by Paul *et al*⁴. However, their formulation of the compound as $\text{BiCl}_3 \cdot (\text{CH}_3\text{CO})_2\text{O}$ does not explain higher specific conductance ($3.73 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of acetyl chloride solution of bismuth oxychloride compared to that ($5.2 \times 10^{-7} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of pure acetyl chloride. It is observed that the conductance of this solution decreases with time due to the separation of the red viscous liquid. Transport measurements with acetone solution of the red viscous liquid indicate movement of the red colour towards anode and increase in the concentration of bismuth in the anode compartment. The analyses of solutions in the anode and cathode compartments give the ratio of Cl:Bi in the anionic species as 3.1. Transport experiments with solution of bismuth oxychloride in acetyl chloride also show net transport of bismuth to the anode, indicating the presence of bismuth containing anionic species. These observations may be interpreted as evidence in support of the formation of BiOCl_2^- and BiOCl_3^{--} in acetyl chloride solution of bismuth oxychloride.

This work was supported by a grant from the Department of Atomic Energy, Govt. of India.

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Received October 3, 1966.